

A linguistic Analysis of Commercial Adverts in English, Arabic and Russian

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : English , Arabic and Russian, Advertise , Linguistics</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5595364</p>	<p><i>Our research study is analyzing highly important field for Arab world these days as a source of foreign currency so this study helps in developing adverting and sure will help in increasing the foreign currency. Using three different languages is highly useful for knowing practically the linguistics in foreign languages like English, Arabic and Russian, and learn from them how to use catchy, tricky and smart slogans using linguistics and pictures on the advertise. The results of the research are very useful for advertisement creators and agencies as it guides them how to develop their advertisements to be able to compete internationally. The work consists of an introduction, two chapters, a conclusion, a bibliography and appendixes. The introduction presents the aim, problem, goals, methodology, subject, material of research, etc. The first chapter contains the presentation of the literature study, theoretical part through the historical background of the advertisements and theories of linguistic analysis and some previous studies relating to this topic. The second chapter presents analysis of data, an investigation and discussion of the findings established by this study. The conclusion contains the results of the study, the bibliography lists the literature used.</i></p>

Introduction

No one can deny that advertising well known word for all people around the world, because it is the most powerful and the most dominant. It can reach to the people minds easily twenty-four hour per day with attractive slogans and catchy colors and pictures and tricky ideas.

We can find advertisements everywhere on the streets, TV, radio, newspapers, even on our mobile phones with running applications. So that advertising is very effective and it is worth to be studied to understand the concept and the basics of the advertising.

Advertising used for selling products, also it is a vital method for provide ideas and gain classy human principles. On the other hand, to emphasize on specific principles or habits or used to provide important information to the people.

Ancient humanity knows the advertising very well starting from the Egyptian civilization through many cultures and civilizations. One of the most old printed advertising medium is a Bronze stone plate from China science 4000 B.C drawn on it advertisement for Family called "Liu" selling needles. So the advertising considered of human instinct.

Recently, advertising becomes a science where we can find the beauty of the language and tricky catchy slogans stuck on the brains of the customer's minds. What we are interest in here is the text advertising where linguistic analysis applied to show the principles and the method of creating the ads. Our study interest in tourism advertisements analysis, in three different languages English, Arabic and Russian to show the difference between them in using linguistics, fonts and pictures.

1.2 the purpose of the study

linguistic study of the specifics of tourist advertising in English, Arabic and Russian. This study is to achieve an understanding of the relationship between an analysis of some of the commercial advertisements English, Arabic and Russian (especially the tourism commercial advertisements) and their relationship with that should be effective enough to present a successful advertisement with a linguistically intended message.

1.3 Objectives of the study:

- 1) Determine the linguistic status of advertising.
- 2) Describe the language features of advertising in three languages.
- 3) Give a description of tourist advertising in terms of its functional features.

Review of the Related literature

2.1. Definition of advertisement

The advertisement is studied in many disciplines, namely mass communication, fields related to business administration (i.e., economics, marketing), and linguistics. Advertising is one of world's most pervasive forms of communication. It has become an integral part of human society [Al-Olayan&Karande 2010: 7] many times a day, each and every individual is exposed to advertising in one form or another. Advertisements are broadcast on the Internet, social media networking websites, radio, and television. They appear in newspapers, magazines, food packaging and billboards. Advertisements are, literally, everywhere.

According to the Canadian-US advertising pioneer, John E. Kennedy [1864- 1928] advertisement is paid, non-personal, public communication about causes, goods and services, ideas, organizations, people, and places, through means such as direct mail, telephone, print, radio, television, and internet. An integral part of marketing, advertisements are public notices designed to inform and motivate. Their objective is to change the thinking pattern (or buying behavior) of the recipient, so that he or she is persuaded to take the action desired by the advertiser. When aired on radio or television, an advertisement is called a commercial; it is "salesmanship in print" [John E. Kennedy, 1864 – 1982].

The linguistic definition of commercial advertising: The verb "advertise" is derived from Latin "advertere," which literally means to turn towards. A. Goddard confirms this, saying that "adverts are texts that do their best to get our attention, to make us turn towards them" [Trehan ,2006].

The difference between advertising and advertisement: advertising is a one- way communication as ads agency is responsible for the content of the ads, advertising medium like TV, radio, magazine, newspapers, internet and video games...etc. But advertisement defines as the act of advertising itself.

In simple terms, 'advertisement' is the endorsement and marketing of products, goods and services by using different mediums such as newspaper, television, and the Internet in order to increase their sales. According to Bailey [2010:118] 'advertising is a paid, non-personal message from an identifiable source delivered through a mass mediated channel that is designed to persuade'. Advertisement and the process of advertising are not exclusively devoted to the promotion and selling of products. According to Becker, advertisements are used to give messages to consumers and can assist in creating a strong image of the individual or group, by making consumers 'more favourably disposed in general terms to the advertised product or service' [Becker, 2010: 58] advertisements are used by different groups for different ends. For instance, commercial products are sold by commercial firms, political advertisements are designed to catch individuals' attention in order to gain votes, governments use advertisements to deliver message of safety or public awareness. The significance of advertising and advertisements cannot be denied and it plays a pivotal role in influencing the society [Becker, 2010: 58].

2.2. Historical of advertisement

recently, however, that translation theorists have turned their analytic gaze towards advertising texts as distinct from a wider field of commercial texts. The increasing facility of transnational communication means that the most recent research is moving away from purely linguistic analyses towards a consideration of the inter semiotic or integrated, multimodal nature of advertising text. In relation to inter- and transnational advertising, the cultural complications and impact of advertising translation also have to be taken into account [Torresi, 2009].

An advertising text must be used in accordance to the target society's cultural norms in order to ensure that it delivers its message to the target audience. Translation is considered to be an important part of the advertising industry, as 'for many subject in the informational economy, the language of (native) expression remains the preferred language of (individual) access' [Crystal 2010: 147].

Despite the pervasive feature of advertising, only recently have linguists been interested in it, Kumatoriya continues that since linguists are becoming more and more interested in the study of language use, they show interest in the form and use of advertising language. Consequently, some relevant studies will be discussed here. These are the studies by Leech, Garfinkel, Bergh and Reid, Monnot, Shimp and Preston, and Wicke.

2.3. Function of the advertisement

Leech denotes the language of advertising as loaded language, implying its intention to skew the audience's perception. The audience, when reacting to advertising, is consequently acting in a desired and

expected way. These characteristics correspond with the main goal of advertising, which is described by McQuarrie “communication of meaning is secondary, audience response is primary”.[McQuarrie, 2008].

Jakson refers that to achieve the desired audience response, the language of advertising should comply with the criteria of an effective act of verbal communication [Jakson, 2009] Roman Jakobson determined six language rules, according to which an effective act of communication can be described:

- **The Referential Function:** describes a situation, an object, or a mental state and is oriented toward the context.

- **The Emotive Function:** does not change the denotation of the utterance, but adds the information about the internal state of the speaker and orientates toward the address

- **The Conative Function:** engages the addressee directly and is represented in imperative and vocatives .

- **The Phatic Function:** serves to establish, discontinue, or prolong the communication.

- **The Metalingual Function:** is used to describe and discuss the language itself.

- **The Poetic Function focuses:** on the message for its own sake [Sebeok,1960:350-377].

Advertising gives linguists an excellent opportunity to study the field. According to the Linguistic Society of America “Linguistics is the scientific study of language, and many topics are studied under this umbrella. At the heart of linguistics is the search for the unconscious knowledge that humans have about language and how it is that children acquire it, an understanding of the structure of language. In general and of particular languages, knowledge about how languages vary, and how language influences the way in which we interact with each other and think about the world”[Monica Macaulay and Kristen Syrett, 2003].

method

3.1. Sample of study

After characterizing the major linguistic devices in the theoretical part, their practical use in advertising analyzed. The database of 230 advertisements created by specifically for the purpose of this research. It includes three main languages English, Arabic and Russian analyzing the linguistic meanings of advertising slogans used in three parts (**a hundred ads in English, a hundred ads in Arabic, and thirty ads in Russian**). The data has been collected and obtained randomly with the help of search engines.

Sample of the study gathered from making search on the INTERNET for the following reasons:

1-Internet has very rich material for the three language advertises.

2-Be sure that we got latest advertises, which have new and smart ideas.

3-Opportunity to choose our sample of study between huge numbers of advertises to enrich our research

4-Internet was very vital to get advertises in foreign language like English and Russian.

3.2. Linguistic means used in advertising language

Linguistics used to persuade the audience to buy the product, aiming to change their opinion or attitudes toward a specific type of products. Linguistics enables the sellers to have different ads, attractive, unexpected words and catchy phrases. Leech main principles for advertising were attention value, readability, memorability and selling power [Leech, 1972: 25]. Cook describes it as a type of discourse “it can tell us a good deal about our own society and our own psychology (...). Discourse is text and context together” [Cook 1996: 2-5]. All the above are proofing for the importance of linguistics in our daily life. There are five main categories of linguistic means used in the advertising slogans:

a)Phonological aspect

b)Lexical and morphological aspect

c)Grammatical aspect

d)Syntactic aspect

e)Stylistic aspect[COWIE: 1983].

3.2.1. Phonological aspect

Phonological aspect is a way of making the advertisement phrases memorable for the audience like phrases used in the poetry, if people love it they will never forget it like “I like MD because it’s real economy”. Phonological aspect has some tools like (rhyme, rhythm, alliteration, assonance, graphic aspect of the text and homophones)[HALLIDAY: 1976].

3.2.2. Rhyme

They are words have the same last sound, for example “Blue” and “Flew” ,”Bat” and ”Cat” [KVETKO:2001].

Examples:

1- Ad 16: Sometimes **solving nothing** solves **everything**.

2-Ad 21: Come to Thailand let’s **take a break**

3-Ad 26: **Celebrating** a 100 years of nation’s **awaking**

4-Ad 13: **وجهات جديدة... ومحطات عديدة... وسياحة فريدة** (New destinations ... and many stations ... and unique tourism)

- 5-Ad 26: **صيفك على كيفك!** (Your summer is on your way)
 6-Ad 20: **رياضة-لغة-سيادة** (Sport-Language-Sovereignty)
 7-Ad 2: **Хватит мечтать – пора отдыхать**

3.2.3. Rhythm

Human mind is highly attracted to the rhythm as it knows sounds and words or musical notes used in poetry for example for that it is so memorable for the audience like mother's heartbeat [Cook, Guy, 1996:120].

Examples:

- 1-Ad 14: **We are** upbeat **we are** laid-back **we are** Egypt
 2-Ad 4 : where **fresh** air comes with **fresh** seafood
 3-Ad 29: the best place in the **universe** New Mexico, **Earth**
 4-Ad 3: من قلب مصر الى قلب المملكة: **السياحة الصحراوية**
 5-Ad 91: **السياحة الصحراوية**
 6-Ad 14: [رياضة – لغة – سيادة]
 We didn't find examples of rhythm in Russian.

3.2.4. Alliteration

By using the same sound or sounds, many times especially at the beginning of the word like "Round the rugged rocks the ragged rascal ran" [Cambridge dictionary] [LAKOFF: 1980].

Examples:

- 1-Ad 88: **Scenic-Serene-Sublime** the soul of incredible India
 2-Ad 79: Sri **L**anka a **l**and **l**ike no other
 3-Ad 6: **B**e one with **B**elize
 4-Ad 18: **و**جها**ت** **ج**ديدة... **و**محطات **ع**ديدة... **و**سياحة **ف**ريدة
 5-Ad 41: **س**ريلانكا **ل**كندا **ن**وارا **ل**يا **ب**نتوتا **ل**ومبو
 6-Ad 91: برنامج **ال**رحلات **ال**سياحية **ال**سياحة **ال**صحراوية
 7-Ad 2: **Волна**тур – **ту**ристическое **а**гентство (Wave tour travel agency)

3.2.5. Assonance

Same syllables have the vowels but different consonant like "Back" and "Hat" or different vowels and the same consonant like "Hat" and "Hit", also the same vowel in successive stressed syllables create a vowel harmony like "Cat can catch the Candle" [OGILVY:1985].

Examples:

- 1-(ai) (e) Ad 32: China **l**ike **n**ever **b**efore
 2-(ai) (i) Ad 31: **B**ig and **w**ide open, just like your **k**id's imagination should be
 3-(au) Ad 30: that's the **s**ound of nobody **s**hout**ing**
 4-(y) Ad 1: يوم **ال**سرا**ي**حة **ال**أرد**ن**ي **م**را**ي**تنا **خ**ا**ي**ها **ب**ع**ي**نك
 5-(k) Ad 29: **ت**عرف **ع**لى **م**ل**ك**ة **ال**م**ل**ك**ة**
 7-(d -z) Ad 17: **Д**оставь **з**везд**у**? **В**оз**м**ожно!

3.2.6. Graphic aspect of the text

Graphic and advertising are one part can't separate them as it plays a vital role in advertising success type of writing text, colors, sizes, all these factors are vitals like website named "datasheet for you" can tell "Datasheet 4 u" [PAVLÍK: 2000].

Examples:

English Ads : (15),
 (22), (26), (36), (100)
Arabic Ads (22)

Ad: 15: As shown above it is word “Egypt”, they replaced letter “T” with a known symbol in the ancient pharos civilization this symbol is “the life key”.

Ad 22: As shown above it is word “India”, they replaced letter “I” with a photo of Indian girl playing “Yoga” which is known much in India.

Ad 26 : As shown above it is word “berala”, they replaced letter “L” with a picture of “Palm” which one of the most famous plants in that place.

Ad 100:As shown above it is word “China”, they replaced here two letters “I” and “A” with drawing for traditional Chinese buildings.

Ad 36: As shown above it is word “Turkey”, they replaced letter “T” with a photo of a man spread his arms to form letter “T” this catchy feature of the advertise.

For Arabic ads using graphic aspect of the text is very rare.

Ad 22 : As shown above it is word “الصيف”, “Summer”, they used letter “ف” and draw a sun around it to express about summer season .

For Russian ads we didn’t find the use of graphic aspect.

Using graphic aspect of text in advertises as shown above is to give advertise catchy tricky manner beside distinctivetexts. Graphic of text means using photo or picture or even drawing instead of specific letter and it still clear to the reader to be able to read it, using mind one moment thinking by the reader to the advertise means that the advertise succeeded to be catchy.

Using graphic aspect of text commonly used in “countries” names like “Egypt, India, China and Turkey” they are all have graphic aspect of text used.

3.2.7. Homophones

Two words pronounced similarly but have different spelling, meaning or both. Like “sew” and “sow”. “Sainsbury’s have discovered that the finest whisky is kept under lock and quay” [Myers: 43].

Examples:

We observe that using of homophones in the sample of the study for English, Arabic and Russian ads is null, may be because they are the same advertisement field.

3.3. Lexical and morphological aspect

This part will concentrate on the vocabulary part into nine points as following:

3.3.1. Verb phrase

Finite verb phrase verses non-finite verb phrase like widely used at Ads for simplicity because non-finite verbs do not show tense, person, or number like “You need to paint the whole wall, **starting** from the bottom.” [SOANES: 2004].

Examples:

1-Ad 1: **Seek** higher elevation

2-Ad 2: **Arrived** in search of the ultimate break. **Departedhavingfound** paradise

3-Ad 20: We **do** everything for the perfect holiday

4-Ad 26 : استمتع برحلات تركيا الشتوية: (Enjoy Turkey's winter trips)

5-Ad 9: اكتشف العالم بمنظورنا: (Discover the world from our perspective)

6-Ad 27: احجز خلال يومين و سافر خلال شهرين: (Book within two days and travel within two months)

1-Ad 1 : **Играй**впесок... на Мальдивах (Play in the sand...On the Maldives)

2-Ad 4: **отдыхай**тесудовольствием! (Have a rest with pleasure!)

3-Ad 6 : **Лови**волнупозитива(catch a wave of positive)

Due to our analysis, we can observe that For Arabic Ads verbs Phrase percentage is (16%) but, for English ads verbs phrase percentage is (30.3%). Therefore, English ads use verb phrases more than Arabic Ads by (14.3 %) indicates Arabic ads should use more verb phrase in orderto compensate this difference. Verb phrases in English ads mostly consist of one word and this is the simplest form. Auxiliary verbs used, like “Do”.

1-Noun phrases is much easier than verb phrases, also it gives the text catchy and tricky manner والتاريخ والتسوق والترفيه

2-Ad 17: عروض مميزة لشهر العسل

Ad 16: Волна скидок! приглашаем в лето! (Waveofdiscount! Welcometothsummer) **3.3.2. Nounphrase**
Groupofwordsgatheredinasentencetoformanoun.

Examples:

1-Ad 8: Share your Great **Britain**

2-Ad 26 : **ExperienceMalaysia**

3-Ad 27: **Taste of Iceland**

4-Ad 8: اسبانيا سحر الأندلس

5-Ad 10: اكتشف معنا تنوع المقومات السياحية حيث الطبيعة

6-Ad 12: Путешествие! отдых! (Travels! Recreation)

Due to our analysis, we can observe that for Arabic ads nouns phrase percentage is (29.9%) but, for English ads nouns phrase percentage is (45.5%). Therefore, English ads use nouns phrases more than Arabic ads by (15.6 %) indicates Arabic ads should use more nouns phrase in orderto compensate this difference. as the most tricky part in using nouns is the pre-modified part.

3.3.3. Adjectives

Adjectives are strongly used to show the best in the product by using comparative and superlative adjectives like better, nicer...etc.[VESTERGAARD: 1985].

Examples:

1-Ad 28: **Best** supporting country in a motion picture

2-Ad 29: **The happiest** place on earth

3-Ad 20: we do everything for the **perfect** holiday

4-Ad 23: أجواء عائلية مميزة

5-Ad 28: وجهات جديدة، محطات عديدة، سياحة فريدة

6-Ad 25: دور على حلاوتها حلوة بلدي

7-Ad14: **Превосходные** курорты «всевключено» **на лучших** пляжах! (Excellent all-inclusive resorts on the best beaches!)

8-Ad 9: **Лучшие** курорты мира! (The best resorts in the world!)

9-Ad 22: Ваш **лучший** отдых VITATOUR (Your best vacation with VITA TOUR)

10- Ad 3: **Увлекательные** туры (fascinating tours)

3.3.4. Numerals

Numerals are what some buyers look for in the Ads because it cares with some important information about the ingredients' of the product or vitamins that product will give to us [VESTERGAARD: 1985].

Examples:

1-Ad 9: **five** destinations that share **one** pool.....(Number)

2-Ad 4 : Be **one** with Belize.....(Number)

3-Ad 30: **100** days of polar night magic].....(Number)

4-(14800 ريال)Ad15: [سعر الغرفة] (room price).....(Price)

5-(3-5-2015)Ad 29: تاريخ حجز الغرف (Date of booking of rooms).....(Date)

6-(15 يوم)Ad15: عرض على عدد الأيام للحجز السياح: (Reservation Period)....(Number of days)

ForRussianAdswenoticethatmostoftheadscntainphonenumbers, pricesandinformationaboutdiscount.

1-Ad1: Играй в песочек на Мальдивах (495)987-11-17 (Play in the sand...On the Maldives) (**Phone number**)

2-Ad 11: Не знаете куда отправить ребенка летом? 18900 руб (Do not know where to send a child in the summer?)(**Prices**)

3-Ad 9: **Лучшие** курорты мира! 3% - 5% (the best resorts in the world!)(**Discount**)

Number ‘one’ repeated in the sample of the study for English and Arabic Ads to show or describe case like following:

English Ads

Ad 9: five destinations that share one pool, using number one here supporting the metaphor to give tricky and catchy slogan.

Ad 6: Be one with Belize, using number one here is to make the idea of assuring how the ‘Belize ‘ can give privacy by using number one on the ads.

Arabic Ads

Usage of number one was only for persuading the audience like the following:

Ad: كل ما تتمناه في مكان واحد (Everything you wish in one place)

Finally, Number one also used for preference.

As we can notice from the above examples the difference between using numerals in English, Arabic and Russian ads, as in English ads numbers used for insuring the idea of the advertise but, in Arabic ads they used numerals as prices, period or date and this is due to the economic environment in Arabian world. Arabic ads used prices and number of days as a catchy way to attract the audience. Russian ads did not interested in prices as it interested in mentioning the telephone numbers of traveling agencies this indicates that in Russia there are many legal traveling agencies and the government of Russia highly interested in supporting tourism agencies. In Russia, the price is not very important but the destination is more important.

3.3.5. Foreign words

To insure the origin of the product this will indicate for sure for the quality of the product like “Vorfahren wie in einer Limousine” (In German).

Examples:

1-Ad43: **Yalla** Turkey

Yalla is an Arabic word originally in common speech “يلا” mean “هيا” in English means “Let’s go”

2-Ad73: **Vallarta Nayarit** Mexico

“Vallarta Nayarit” are Spanish words was necessary because it is a place in Mexico.

3-Ad75: Explore the land of **Maharajas**

Maharajas is an ancient word related to the Indian traditional culture.

4-Ad 6: العطلة أحلا في ديزني لاند

“ديزني لاند” is originally an English word of the famous amusement place in USA “Disney Land”

5-Ad 32: عيش الخيال في بودابست

“بودابست” it is a Hungarian word written in Arabic letters.

1-Ad 33 : عيش الخيال في سانتوريني

“سان توريني” it is a **Greek** word “**Σαντορίνη**” written in Arabic letters. (transliteration)

2-Ad 1 : Играй в песок... на Мальдивах

The Maldives is originally in the Maldivian language “**ދިވެހިރާއްޖޭގެ ޖަދުވަލު**”.

3-Ad13: Испания – отдых, который вы заслужили! (Spain, holidays which you deserve!)

4-Испания originally it is Spanish word means Spain (España).

5-Ad19: пора отдохнуть в Египте! (It is time to rest in Egypt!)

Египет originally it is Coptic word.

3.3.6. Intertextuality and Idiomatic constructions

Using famous popular phrases for people in advertising is a smart trick because audience will remember the product all the time joining it to the original phrase, like “creativity is our target pass it on” it is like a quote of Albert Einstein which is “creativity is contagious pass it on”.

“Actions speak louder than words” this is a popular idiom means that People’s intentions can be judged better by what they do than what they say.

Ad 26: **Дождаться у моря погоды в Испании**

This idiomatic construction means “to indulge in vain hopes, wait in vain for something, look for dead men’s shoes, whistle for a wind for the world, to beat a path to your door “. Here we can see the change of tense and aspect that creates an idea about perfect vacation.

Ad28: Лучшее один раз увидеть

As we can see it is only one part of a very famous saying and idiomatic construction that means “picture is worth a thousand words”. This slogan makes you get a real idea of some thing or event, one has to see or watch it rather than rely on someone else’s opinion.

For the sample study of English and Arabic ads, we did not find any Intertextuality and Idiomatic constructions.

3.3.7. Formation of new words and phrases

Best examples in this is new created words known for all peoples used these days like “Google” , “hash tag”...etc.

Examples:

For the sample study of English, Russian and Arabic ads, we did not find any formation of new words and phrases.

3.3.8. Collocations

Like “a combination of words in language, that happens very often and more frequently than would happen by chance” [Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary 2001]. People used to hear “hard forest” not “strong forest” [WIDDOWSON: 1996].

Examples:

1-Ad 33: where **fresh air** comes with fresh seafood

Here we used to say fresh air not pure air or clean air so this is a good collocation example.

2-Ad 34: Bermuda seems like such a **quiet place**

We used to say quiet place not calm or silent place.

For the sample study of English, Russian and Arabic ads, we did not find any collocation phrases.

3.4. Grammatical aspect

There are four types of sentences **Declarative**, which it is normal for the subject to be present and to precede the verb. **Interrogative**, formally marked in one of two ways: yes-no. **Imperative**, it is normally, have no overt grammatical subject, and verb has the base form. **Exclamatives**, phrase introduced by what or how, usually with subject-verb order [Quirk-1990].

Examples:

1-**Dec.** Ad 37: Short break long lasting joy

2-**Dec.** Ad 48: Greece the true experience

3-**Dec.** Ad 24: عروض الصيف شرق آسيا:

4-**Dec.** Ad 22 : Ваш лучший отдых Vita Tour (your best vacation with Vita Tour)

5-**Int.** Ad 64: New Zealand Why not?

6-**Int.** Ad 22: Море? я это заслужила (Sea ? I deserved it)

7-**Excl.** Ad 78: Our South Africa your way!

8-**Excl.** Ad 44: تابلند جمال الغروب الذي لا يفوت:

9-**Excl.** Ad 9: Лучшие курорты мира! (the best resorts in the world !)

10-**Excl.** Ad 13: Испания – отдых – который вы заслужили! (Spain, holidays which you deserve!)

11-**Imp.** Ad 1: **Seek** higher elevation

21-**Imp.** Ad 4: **Discover** an island where the treasure isn't hidden

13-**Imp.** Ad 8: **Share** your grate

41-**Imp.** Ad 34: نفس عميق و اذهب الى فيينا:

15-**Imp.** Ad 7: смотри! гордись !запоминай!(Look! Be proud! Remember!)

16-**Imp.** Ad 4: Отдыхайте с удовольствием! (Have a rest with pleasure!)

In English and Arabic there is only one form for the imperatives but in Russian we have two forms (second person singular and second person plural) they are used frequently.

In Arabic ads grammatical aspect (71%) is the percentage of declarative sentences; in the second place we get the imperative sentences with percentage (27%), interrogatives sentences (1%) and exclamation percentage (1%).

While grammatical aspect in English is (68%) the percentage of declarative sentences. In the second place we get the imperative sentences with percentage (25%), interrogatives sentences (4%) and exclamation percentage (3%).

Grammatical aspect in Russian is (20.1 %) percentage which entails declarative, imperative, interrogative and exclamation statements. The fourth and the fifth are Stylistic and Phonological aspects respectively (12.6 % and 10.1 %).

3.5. Syntax aspect

We studied schematic patterning in advertisement represented into two forms which are ellipsis and incomplete sentences.

Ellipsis

When we don't use words we should use like "seen my keys anywhere?" should use "Have you" first, also known as "the omission of part of a structure." [Goddard 1998: 123].

Examples:

1-Ad 18: **Can you** hear the silence?

2-Ad 37: **Can you** take short break for long lasting joy

3-Ad 13: **Could I** ride through town or high above it?

4-Ad 49: حلوة تيا بلدي

5-Ad 58 : سافر معنا الى مدريد :

6-Ad 16: السفر فرصة للارتقاء

7-Ad 16: Волна скидок ! Мы приглашаем вас в лето!

Incomplete sentences

It is a way of creating catchy phrases as text in ads don't stuck to the grammar as it should be, so you can read Ads text without find one of sentences main component.

Examples:

1-Ad 10: You should be here **too**

2-Ad 26: God's own **Berala** country

3-Ad 30: These trees **are** known

4-Ad 25: مدينة أبو ظبي

5-Ad 42: السفر الى دولة اليزيا:

6-Ad 47: اكتشف معنا مدينة قبرشلونة

We can conclude that the difference between ellipsis and incomplete sentences is clear that ellipsis where the sentence is missed its first part if it is a question like “have you...?” “Should you...?” For incomplete sentence, we do not actually follow the rules of the grammar so we can finish reading the sentence without finding any “Verb” for example.

3.6. Stylistic aspect

3.6.1. Simile

Using Simile in the advertise text to give the receiver good image in mind when used as a comparison with something else will know and familiar to the receiver like compare with “heaven, paradise...etc.” and this is the reason behind highly usage of word “Like” in our sample of the study. In addition, Simile used to show preference, finally we can conclude that both usage of simile is a way to attract and persuade the receiver. Examples to clarify simile usage in texts “breakfast without orange juice is like a day without sunshine”. It depends on the comparison between two things using “as...as”, “like”, “than” [Myers1997:125].

Examples:

- 1-Ad 7 : Bermuda seems **like** such a quiet place
- 2-Ad 23: Nothing **like** making exotic new friends
- 3-Ad 39: Big and wide open, lust **like** your kid’s imagination should be
- 4-Ad 56: There is nothing **like** Australia
- 5-Ad 79: Sri Lanka a land **like** no other
- 6-Ad100: China **like** never before

7-Ad 6: العطلة أحلا في ديزني لاند:

8-Ad 9 : أجمل رحلات نصف العام :

In Russian we didn’t find examples with simile.

3.6.2. Hyperbole

We sometimes do this to emphasize something, to add humor or to gain attention, like “We drove for hours without stopping and I nearly died of hunger”[Wales, 2001].

Examples:

- 1-Ad 3: Arrived in search of the ultimate break. Departed having found **paradise**
- 2-Ad 4: Discover an island where the **treasure** is not hidden
- 3-Ad 3: السياحة معنا بنكهة خاص:
- 4-Ad 70 تركيا جنة الأرض:
- 5-Ad 50: نور الهدى:

3.6.3. Personification

The definition of personification in English is the description of an object or an idea as if it had human characteristic. Also imaginary being represented as a thing or abstraction.

- 1-Ad 11: Life begins at the end of your comfort **zone**
- 2-Ad 28: the daily **grind** is far behind
- 3-Ad 30: these trees **know**
- 4-Ad 1: السياحة مرابتنا خليها بعيونك:
- 5-Ad 33: عيش الذكريات في سان توريني)
- 6-Ad 32: عيش الخيال في بودابست:
- 7-Ad16: Волна скидок! приглашаем в лето! (Wave of discounts! Welcome to the summer!)

3.6.4. Metaphor

Metaphor describes a person or object by referring to something that is considered to have similar characteristics to that person or object

Examples:

- 1-Ad 13: **Ride** through town or high above it
- 2-Ad 15: we are **ancient** we are **young** we are Egypt
- 3-Ad 51: there are **getaways** and then there are here
- 4-Ad 4: من قلب المملكة الى قلب مصر:
- 5-Ad 12: اليونان بوابة أوروبا:
- 6-Ad 28: رحلة مذاق أوروبا:
- 7-Ad24: Ничто так не **окрыляет**, как **путешествие**! Nothing so covers as a journey!
- 8-Ad 17: Достать **звезду**? Возможно! Get a star? Perhaps!

3.6.5. Metonymy

Definition of the Metonymy is the act of referring to something using a word that describes one of its qualities or features. Like “crown” word it could be in place of “the royal person” or “white house” in place of “president”. It is importance as it helps us think about people and things in creative ways so that we recognize how they are sometimes so connected that you can substitute one thing for the other in a sentence. Used to attract the receiver [TRUP: 1990].

Examples:

For the sample study of Arabic and Russian ads we did not find any metonymy.

1-Ad 82: Hong Kong the river of the **orient**

2-Ad 75: explore the land of **Maharajas** (Maharajas related to India)

3.6.6. Antithesis

Antithesis defined as a way of speech use the word or idea and it is opposite to achieve the effects of emphasizing like “we must live together as brothers or perish together as fools” Martin Luther king. Antithesis usage in Advertise text to rich, and to emphasize the idea of contrast by parallel structures of the contrasted phrases or clauses [TRUP: 1990].

Examples:

1-Ad 37: **short** break **long** lasting joy

2-Ad 40: the best way to **recharge** is by **unplug**

3-Ad 87: تركيا حضارة الشرق وسحر الغرب

4-Ad 27: Меняем **зиму** на **лето**

5-Ad 29: Отдых на Ямайке **или так, или с нами**

3.6.7. Polysemy and homonymy

Homonymy is the relation between phonological similar words but they are differing in meaning but polysemy is the words have closely related senses.

Example:

For the sample study of English, Russian and Arabic ads, we did not find any polysemy or homonymy.

Result**Analysis results of English Ads**

From the data analyzed by the researcher, the results reveal that the most frequently used type of linguistic structure is the **lexical and morphological aspect** (phrase verbs, phrase nouns and adjectives) around (32.8 %), Which implies that advertisers try to attract the clients by using complex nouns and giving these nouns the appropriate adjective to make it more appealing to the audience. The second type is the **phonological** (rhyme, rhythm, assonance and alliteration) with percentage around (21.3 %) which in my opinion should be the most frequently used type, since it involves the musical nature of the words. The third type is the **grammatical** structure (15.5 %) (imperative, declarative and exclamation) considering the use the proper form of sentence is somehow attractive to the eyes and ears of the person receiving the information. The forth type is the **stylistic** (15.4 %) (personification and metaphors) by giving the places of attraction a touch of human cover and using metaphors just like poets use in poetry to give the sentence an artistic style. Finally the least used type is the **syntactic structure** (15.1 %) (Ellipsis and schematic patterning) used to make the experience in the sentence more personal.

Lexical and morphological aspect

the highest percentage was for numeral by (1.9%) then for phrase nouns by (45.5%), Phrase verbs (30.3%), adjectives (21.3%), and finally idiomatic constructions (0.5%). We can observe that Ads, Doesn't contain any of (collocations, foreign words, intertextuality or new words or phrases). **Stylistic** highest was for metaphors (47.5%), personification (17.2%) then hyperbole (14.1%), Simile (10.1%), polysemy and homonymy by (6.1%) on the end comes lowest percentages for Antithesis by (3%). **Syntactic aspect** in the first place

schematicpattering comes with the highest percentage (62%), ellipsis (16%) and incomplete sentences comes with percentage (19%). **Grammatical aspect** (68%) is the percentage of declarative sentences; in the second place we get the imperative sentences with percentage (25%), Interrogatives sentences (4%) and Exclamation percentage (3%). the **phonological aspect** assonance percentage on the Ads, was (32%), rhythm (24.1%), rhyme (21.2%), alliteration (15%), homophones (4.4%), finally comes transliteration by (3.6%) from all of the above we conclude that English ads, mainly depend on the following; (noun phrase, metaphors, assonance with schematic pattern all in declarative sentences.

Analysis results of Arabic Ads

From the data analyzed by the researcher, the results reveal that the most frequently used type of linguistic structure is the **lexical and morphological aspect** (phrase verbs, phrase nouns and adjectives) around (32.9 %), Which implies that advertisers try to attract the clients by using complex nouns and giving these nouns the appropriate adjective to make it more appealing to the audience. The second type is the **stylistic** (18.9 %) (personification and metaphors) by giving the places of attraction a touch of human cover and using metaphors just like poets use in poetry to give the sentence an artistic style. The third type is the **phonological** (rhyme, rhythm, assonance and alliteration) with percentage around (17.1 %) which in my opinion should be the most frequently used type, since it involves the musical nature of the words. The fourth type is the **syntax structure**(16.5 %) (ellipsis and schematicpattering) used to make the experience in the sentence more personal. Finally the least used type is the **grammatical** structure (14.6 %) (imperative, declarative and exclamation) considering the use the proper form of sentence is somehow attractive to the eyes and ears of the person receiving the information.

Lexical and morphological aspect the highest percentage was for numeral by (38.4%)then for phrase nouns by (29.9%), phrase verbs (16%), adjectives (11.2%), idiomatic constructions (4%) and finally collocations (0.4%). We can observe that ads don't contains any of (foreign word, intertextuality or new words or phrases) this gives us an indication how the Arabian tourism market highly interested in prices, which could be because of the current economic situations on these countries. **Stylistic** highest was for personification (44.2%) then metaphors (34.1%), hyperbole (12.4%), simile (7.8%) on the end comes lowest percentages for antithesis by (0.8%) and Polysemy and homonymy by (0.8%). **Syntactic aspect** in the first place schematicpattering comes with the highest percentage (58.9%), ellipsis (25.9%) and incomplete sentences comes with percentage (15.2%). **Grammatical aspect**

(71%) is the percentage of declarative sentences; in the second place we get the imperative sentences with percentage (27%), interrogatives sentences (1%) and exclamation percentage (1%). the **phonological aspect** Assonance percentage on the Ads. is (25%), transliteration (24%), rhyme (23.3%), rhythm (11.2%), homophones (0.9%). From all of the above we can say that Arabic ads. Mainly depend on the numerals, graphic of the text, assonance, personification, schematic pattern all included on declarative sentence. Also usage of interrogative and exclamation sentences are very rare, also for **lexical and morphological aspect** we didn't found any foreign words, Intertextuality, formatting of new words.

Analysis results of Russian Ads

The analysis results show that the most frequently used aspect in the study sample is the lexical and morphological aspect percentage is (36.1 %) which entails the utilization of verb phrase, noun phrase, adjectives, numerals and collocations. The second most used aspect is the syntax aspect percentage is (21 %) which entails schematic patterning, ellipsis and Incomplete sentences. The third aspect is the grammatical aspect percentage is (20.1 %) which entails declarative, imperative, interrogative and exclamation statements. The fourth and the fifth are stylistic and Phonological aspects respectively (12.6 % and 10.1 %).

From these percentages, it is clear that the Russian ads tend to use lexical aspect more often than any other aspect. Where noun phrases, adjectives, collocations helps the advertiser to present his/her idea clearly to persuade the audience. Finally, using schematic pattern gives tricky and catchy style for the ads.

Discussion

In our practical part we analyzed 230 Ads in three languages (English, Arabic and Russian). We described advertising slogans due to five major aspects, which are phonological aspect, grammatical, syntax aspect, stylistic aspect and lexical and morphological aspect. This study was a trial to understand the difference between the Arabian and foreign ads and to find the points of strength and weakness in advertising markets. The study has five tables due to the five aspects, calculated the frequency of linguistic means.

The methodology used in this study was analytical method as we apply linguistic tools to the ads. In addition, calculated the percentage of using every tool of them to recognize the core difference between them.

From the graph we observe that Arabic Ads Analysis exceeds by percentage the English Ads due to the following aspects (Stylistic, Syntax, Lexical and morphological) but only phonological aspect where analysis of English Ads exceeds Arabic Ads. For that we will mention in the following paragraph the differences due to English Analysis as already Arabic ads analysis already exceeded. for phonological aspect English Ads, exceeded Arabic ads by (2%) that because of the increase in assonance percentage over Arabic ads by (7%), increase in rhythm by (12.9%), increase in hyperbole by (3.5%) this means that English Ads depend on catchy phrases and musical words. For Grammatical analysis difference between Arabic Ads and English ads is in using interrogative sentences where English ads higher than Arabic ads by (3%), also for exclamation sentences by (2%). For syntax aspect English ads higher than Arabic ads by (3.1%) for schematic pattern, also by (3.8%) for incomplete sentences. For stylistic aspect English ads was higher than Arabic ads due to metaphors by (13.4%) for simile by(2.2%), for Polysemy and homonymy by (5.3%), for antithesis by (2.2%) . For lexical and morphological aspect English ads are higher than Arabic Ads by (36.5%) this is very ambient difference reflect what is exactly the customer interested in, also this emphasize the idea we mentioned above in the Arabic Ads analysis conclusion , then for phrase nouns by (15.6%), Phrase verbs (14.3%), adjectives (10.1%). from all of the above we conclude that market needs direct the sellers to advertise in the proper way to attract the buyer, this study gives us some important notes about the community where English ads offered and Arabic community that economical factor for the Arabic community is dominant that is because of the current economic situation. second there is no much care about constructing sentences as we can found that English Ads exceeds Arabic ads due to point of view of (verbs, nouns and adjectives) summed by (40%) this very huge percentage in my opinion. In my opinion we should emphasize on taking care of using right Arabian sentences, increase or usage of assonance, alliteration and Rhythm. Finally using schematic pattern gives tricky and catchy style for the ads. See the figure below:

In the following conclusion, we have detailed difference percentages between every type of

linguistic analysis in English, Arabic ads. The result of the study was tricky as Arabic ads get the highest percentage over the English ads but technically English ads more powerful for example in the lexical and morphological aspect Arabic ads get the highest percentage of numerals but English ads due to the study and the analysis is much powerful.

We didn't compare results of English and Arabic data with Russian because the number of ads is different, much less. Lexical and morphological aspect in Russian is more important (36%). Grammar and syntax are almost the same percentage (20% and 21%). Phonological and stylistic aspects are (10% and 13%) which are less than the others.

Conclusion

Sample of study of our research was in three languages English, Arabic and Russian. The data has been collected and obtained randomly with the help of search engines in internet. The analysis determined five main linguistic categories (phonological aspect, lexical and morphological aspect, syntactic aspect, stylistic aspect, grammatical aspect) all listed in tables, have the three languages on them in the following order(English, Arabic and Russian). The theoretical part used examples from the analyzing tables to clarify the meaning of every method of analysis. And we observe that language, nowadays, is not a mere tool of communication rather it has become a commodity to earn money. It is, in the business world, the most influential device of publicity owing to its attractive nature.

Advertising is becomes very important to persuade the audiences to have the product, we can find ads everywhere, all the time. These days advertising effected by the humans growing as there are many aspects, which manage and control these ads.

This study was a trial to understand the difference between foreign ads.

In conclusion for the practical part we have detailed difference percentages between every type of linguistic analysis in English and Arabic ads. We also did statistics for Russian ads.

The commercials affect the public view about their livelihood. They develop a certain point of view about different products. Choice and arrangement of words is the art to inculcate the desired outcomes.

Appealing language, strong metaphors, use of idioms and collocations attract the viewers' attention and predispose them.

Effectiveness of advertisements has always remained an important and debatable issue in the advertising world and International companies nowadays need to communicate with consumers of different languages and cultures in order to sell their products in different markets. Although they can make this communication through advertising that plays a key role within the framework of international marketing strategies and numerous studies have resulted in questionable and conflicting results [Dixit, 2005].

The importance of creativity in advertising has been much realized among advertising practitioners and academia [Ang et al., 2007]. Advertising practitioners consider creativity in advertising as a remedy for breaking through the greater media clutter [Pieters and others, 2002]. Similarly, every advertising text book usually contains one or two chapters on advertising creativity [Smith & Yang, 2004]. In this sense, creativity in advertising is considered as an effective tool to break through the media clutter, capture consumers' attention, build an impression and lead to more effectiveness of an advertising campaign [Till & Baack, 2005].

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